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**BIOACTIVE «NAFTUSSYA» WATER AND PHYTOCOMPOSITION
“BALM TRUSKAVETS” CAUSES SIMILAR ADAPTOGENIC
EFFECTS ON SOME PARAMETERS OF THE HUMAN BODY**

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**БІОАКТИВНА ВОДА «НАФТУСЯ» ТА ФІТОКОМПОЗИЦІЯ
«БАЛЬЗАМ ТРУСКАВЕЦЬКИЙ» СПРИЧИНЯЮТЬ ПОДІБНІ
АДАПТОГЕННІ ЕФЕКТИ НА ДЕЯКІ ПАРАМЕТРИ ОРГАНІЗМУ
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**BIOAKTIVNAYA VODA «NAFTUSSYA» I PHYTOCOMPOZICIYA
«BALZAM TRUSKAVECKIY» VYZYVAIUT SХОDNYE
АДАПТИВНЫЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ НА НЕКОТОРЫЕ ПАРАМЕТРЫ
ОРГАНИЗМА ЧЕЛОВЕКА**

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Summary/Резюме

Background. From previous studies, it is known about the adaptogenic properties of Naftussya bioactive water and the Ukrainian phytocomposition “Balm Truskavets”. Both adaptogens have a common component of the composition - polyphenols, which suggests the existence of similar effects on the parameters of the body responsible for adaptation. The *purpose* of this study is to test the hypothesis. *Material and methods.* The *object* of clinical-physiological observation were 30 practically healthy individuals of both sexes with dysfunction of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex as a manifestation of maladaptation. Before and after a one-week course of using Balm (10 people) or Naftussya water (20 people), plasma levels of the main adaptation hormones, parameters of electroencephalogram (EEG), heart rate variability (HRV), phagocytosis, leukocytogram, as well as acupuncture and bioelectrophotonics were recorded. *Results.* 39 parameters (18 EEGs, 8 HRVs, 5 biophysical, 4 phagocytosis, as well as the leukocytary adaptation index, triiodothyronine, testosterone and cortisol) were identified, the physiologically favorable changes of which are common to both adaptogenic agents. *Conclusion.* The influence of adaptogens of various nature on the state of adaptation of the body is non-specific and is implemented through the neuro-endocrine-immune complex.

Key words: *Naftussya bioactive water, phytocomposition “Balm Truskavets”, neuro-endocrine-immune complex.*

Передумови. З попередніх досліджень відомо про адаптогенні властивості біоактивної води Нафтуса і української фітокомпозиції “Бальзам Трускавець”. Обидва адаптогени мають спільний компонент складу – поліфеноли, що навіює думку про існування подібних ефектів на параметри організму, відповідальні за адаптацію. Перевірка гіпотези є метою даного дослідження. *Матеріал і методи.* Об’єктом клініко-фізіологічного спостереження були 30 практично здорових осіб обох статей з дисфункцією нейро-ендокринно-імунного комплексу як проявом дизадаптації. До і після тижневого курсу вживання бальзаму (10 осіб) або води Нафтуса (20 осіб) реєстрували рівні в плазмі головних гормонів адаптації, параметри електроенцефалограми (ЕЕГ), варіабельності ритму серця (ВРС), фагоцитозу, лейкоцитограми, а також акупунктури і біоелектрорифтоніки. *Результати.* Виявлено 39 параметрів (18 ЕЕГ, 8 ВРС, 5 біофізичних, 4 фагоцитозу, а також лейкоцитарний індекс адаптації, трийодтиронін, тестостерон і кортизол), фізіологічно сприятливі зміни яких спільні для обох адаптогенних засобів. *Висновок.* Вплив адаптогенів різної природи на стан адаптації організму має неспецифічний характер і реалізується через нейро-ендокринно-імунний комплекс.

Ключові слова: *біоактивна вода Нафтуса, фітокомпозиція “Бальзам Трускавець”, нейро-ендокринно-імунний комплекс.*

Предпосылки. Из предыдущих исследований известно об адаптогенных свойствах биоактивной воды Нафтуса и украинской фитокомпозиции “Бальзам Трускавец”. Оба адаптогена имеют общий компонент – полифенолы, что приводит к мысли о существовании подобных эффектов на параметры организма, ответственные за адаптацию. Проверка гипотезы – *цель* данного исследования. *Материал и способы.* Объектом клинико-физиологического наблюдения были 30 практически здоровых лиц обоих полов с дисфункцией нейроэндокринно-иммунного комплекса как проявлением дизадаптации. До и после недельного курса употребления бальзама (10 человек) или воды Нафтуса (20 человек) регистрировали уровни в плазме главных гормонов адаптации, параметры электроэнцефалограммы (ЭЭГ), вариабельности ритма сердца (ВРС), фагоцитоза, лейкоцитограммы, а также акупунк. *Результаты.* Выявлено 39 параметров (18 ЭЭГ, 8 ВРС, 5 биофизических, 4 фагоцитоза, а также лейкоцитарный индекс адаптации, трийодтиронин, тестостерон и кортизол), физиологически благоприятные изменения которых общие для обоих адаптогенных средств. *Вывод.* Воздействие адаптогенов различной природы на состояние адаптации организма имеет неспецифический характер и реализуется через нейроэндокринно-иммунный комплекс.

Ключевые слова: *биоактивная вода Нафтуса, фитокомпозиция “Бальзам Трускавец”, нейро-эндокринно-иммунный комплекс.*

Introduction

Previous experimental and clinical-physiological studies have shown that the Ukrainian phytocomposition “Balm Truskavets” (ТУ У 15.8-24055046-

005:2009, produced by private research and production enterprise “Ukrainian Balms”, Mykolaïv), increases the resistance of the patients with maladaptation to **bacterial** infection [], i.e.

corresponds to one of the attributes of adaptogens: the ability to cause a state of non-specifically increased resistance of the body to the influence of adverse environmental factors of a physical, chemical and **biological** nature [1,33,46]. An even stronger proof of the adaptogenic ability of the phytocomposition is an increase in the leukocytary Popovych's **adaptation** index, which reflects the quantitative assessment of qualitative changes in the body's general adaptive reactions, namely, a decrease in the share of pathological and premorbid (disharmonious) reactions and an increase in the share of normal (harmonious) reactions [19,20,33]. The adaptogenic effect of "Balm Truskavets" is accompanied by favorable changes in the parameters of neuro-endocrine regulation, as well as acupuncture and bioelectrophotonics [].

The most investigated medicinal herbs for their adaptogenic activity are *Eleutherococcus senticosus*, *Panax ginseng*, *Withania somnifera*, *Schisandra chinensis*, *Rhaponticum carthamoides*, *Lepidium meyenii*, and *Rhodiola* spp. Phytochemicals that have been demonstrated adaptogenic properties mainly belong to polyphenolic compounds [].

Currently, we do not have data on the chemical composition of the "Balm Truskavets". In the composition of its predecessor and analogue "Balm Kryms'kyi", polyphenols were detected in the amount of 4 mg/L compared to 7 mg/L in ginseng tincture (produced by "Lubnykhimfarm") [1]. It is interesting that polyphenols in amounts of 0,039±0,28 mg/L were also found in the composition of bioactive Naftussya water [18,27,28,61], the adaptogenic properties of which have long been known [19,25,33,54].

This suggests the existence of joint

effects of both adaptogens, the purpose of this study is to verify this.

Material and research methods

The object of observation were employees of the clinical sanatorium "Moldova" and PrJSC "Truskavets' Spa": 16 women 25-76 years and 14 men 31-69 years. The volunteers were considered practically healthy (without a clinical diagnosis), but the initial testing revealed deviations from the norm in a number of parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex (details follow) as a manifestation of maladaptation.

In the morning in basal condition registered kirlianogram by the method of GDV by the device of "GDV Chamber" ("Biotechprogress", SPb, RF). Method of GDV, essence of which consists in registration of photoelectronic emission of skin, induced by high-frequency electromagnetic impulses, allows to estimate integrated psycho-somatic state of organism. Program estimates also Energy and Asymmetry of virtual Chakras [Korotkov KG, 2001; 2007; 2014].

Then recorded simultaneously electrocardiogram (ECG) and electroencephalogram (EEG). ECG recorded during 7 min in II lead to assess the parameters of heart rate variability (HRV) (hardware-software complex "CardioLab+HRV" produced by "KhAI-Medica", Kharkiv). For further analysis the temporal and spectral parameters were selected [Baevskiy RM & Ivanov GG, 2001;HRV, 1996; Berntson GG et al., 1997]. EEG recorded a hardware-software complex "NeuroCom Standard" (KhAI Medica, Kharkiv) monopolar in 16 loci (Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, F7, F8, C3, C4, T3, T4, P3, P4, T5, T6, O1, O2) by 10-20 international system, with the reference electrodes A and Ref on the earlobes. Two minutes after the eyes had been closed, 25 sec of artifact free EEG data were collected by computer. In addition to

the received parameters, we calculated coefficient of Asymmetry (As) and Laterality Index (LI) for power spectral density (PSD) each rhythm using equations:

$$As, \% = 100 \cdot (Max - Min) / Min; LI, \% = Y [200 \cdot (Right - Left) / (Right + Left)] / 8.$$

We calculated for HRV and each locus EEG the Entropy (h) of normalized PSD using Popovych's IL [Gozhenko AI et al., 2021] formulas based on classic Shannon's CE [1948] formulas:

$$hHRV = - [PSHF \cdot \log_2 PSHF + PSLF \cdot \log_2 PSLF + PSVLF \cdot \log_2 PSVLF + PSULF \cdot \log_2 PSULF] / \log_2 4;$$

$$hEEG = - [PSD\delta \cdot \log_2 PSD\delta + PSD\theta \cdot \log_2 PSD\theta + PSD\alpha \cdot \log_2 PSD\alpha + PSD\beta \cdot \log_2 PSD\beta] / \log_2 4.$$

Electroconductivity (EC) recorded in follow points of acupuncture: Pg(ND), TR(X) and MC(AVL) at Right and Left side. Used complex "Medissa". For each pair, the Laterality Index was calculated according to the already mentioned formula

In portion of capillary blood counted up Leukocytogram (LCG) (Eosinophils, Stub and Segmentonuclear Neutrophils, Lymphocytes and Monocytes) and calculated its Adaptation Index as well as Strain Index by Popovych IL [22,33].

$$Strain\ Index - 1 = [(Eo/3,5 - 1)^2 + (SN/3,5 - 1)^2 + (Mon/5,5 - 1)^2 + (Leu/6 - 1)^2] / 4.$$

Parameters of phagocytic function of neutrophils estimated as described by Kovbasnyuk MM [Kul'chyns'kyi AB et al.,

2016]. The objects of phagocytosis served daily cultures of Staphylococcus aureus (ATCC N 25423 F49) as typical specimen for Gram-positive Bacteria and Escherichia coli (O55 K59) as typical representative of Gram-negative Bacteria. Take into account the following parameters of Phagocytosis: activity (percentage of neutrophils, in which found microbes - Hamburger's Phagocytic Index PhI), intensity (number of microbes absorbed one phagocytes - Microbial Count MC or Right's Index) and completeness (percentage of dead microbes - Killing Index KI). On the basis of the registered partial parameters of phagocytosis, taking into account the content of neutrophils (N) in 1 L of blood, the integral parameter - the bactericidal capacity of neutrophils - was calculated by the formula:

$$BCCN (10^9\ Bact/L) = N (10^9/L) \cdot PhI (\%) \cdot MC (Bact/Phag) \cdot KI (\%) \cdot 10^{-4}.$$

At last in portion of venous blood determined plasma levels of major hormones of adaptation: Cortisol, Testosterone, Aldosterone, Triiodothyronine and Calcitonin (by the ELISA with the use of analyzer "RT-2100C" (ChPR) and corresponding sets of reagents from "Алкор Био", XEMA Co, Ltd and DRG International Inc).

After the initial testing, during the week 20 volunteers (10 women 33-76 y and 10 men 37-69 y) used Naftussya water (250 ml 1 hour before meals three times a day), and the other 10 (6 women

Table 1

Quantification of General Adaptation Reaction of Organism, first version [22]

Leukocytogram Lymphocytes level, %	General Adaptation Reaction of Organism	Eosinophils and Stub Neutrophils: 1÷6 %; Monocytes: 4÷7 %; Leukocytes: 4÷8 G/l	Eosinophils and Stub Neutrophils: <1; >6; Monocytes: <4; >7; Leukocytes: <4; >8 G/l
<21	Stress	1,22	0,02
21÷27	Training	1,46	0,74
28÷33	Quiet Activation	1,95	0,98
34÷43,5	Heightened Activation	1,70	0,90
≥44	Overactivation	0,26	

25ч63 y and 4 men 31ч60 y) “Balm Truskavets” (5 mL pre-diluted in 250 ml of boiled tap water according to a similar scheme. The next morning after completing the treatment, retesting was performed.

Reference values are taken from the database of our laboratory (EEG, GDV, Immunity) or instructions (HRV & ELISA). Results processed using the software

package “Statistica 6.4”.

Results and discussion

According to the algorithm of Truskavetsian Scientific School, at the preparatory stage of data analysis the registered parameters (variables) were normalized, which allowed their correct comparison [22,48]. Further, profiles of normalized parameters were created, the levels of which differ significantly before and after treatment (regardless of the nature of the adaptogen), as well as several parameters which according to the following discriminant analysis were still **recognizable**, despite the **insignificant** value of Student’s t criterion (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Profiles of variables whose normalized levels ($Z \pm SE$) are decreasing under the influence of the treatment. Clusters B+/A0 and B0/A-

Fig. 2. Profiles of variables whose normalized levels ($Z \pm SE$) are increasing under the influence of the treatment. Cluster B0/A+

Fig. 3. Profiles of variables whose normalized levels ($Z \pm SE$) are increasing under the influence of the treatment. Cluster B-/A0

Another approach to quantifying effects is to calculate the direct differences between the final and initial parameters levels of each patient (Fig. 4).

Next, 39 parameters were grouped into 4 clusters, of which 2 are enhancing and 2 are reducing (Fig. 3 and Table 2).

In particular, the moderately **increased** levels of plasma triiodothyronine,

Fig. 4. The clusters of effects of the treatment as direct differences of normalized variables ($Z \pm SE$)

Fig. 5. Clusters of adaptogenic effects. The number of variables is indicated in parentheses

At the same time, **normal** levels of plasma testosterone, four HRV-markers of vagal tone **also decrease**, albeit slightly. This is accompanied by left lateralization (negative sign of symmetry / lateralization indices) of initially symmetrical (quasi-zero symmetry / lateralization indices) EEG β -rhythm, electrical conductivity of acupuncture points MC(AVL) and virtual seventh Chakra (cluster B0/A-).

PSD of β -rhythm in T6 locus as well as LF and HF bands of HRV, Entropy of Gas Discharge Image in Left projection (HGDI L) and right-sided (positive sign of symmetry index) asymmetry of the virtual third Chakra are completely **normalized** (cluster B+/A0).

Instead, the significantly **reduced** levels of the Popovych's adaptation index and epy bactericidal capacity of neutrophils (BCCN) vs both *E. coli* and *Staph. aureus* **increase** significantly, still remaining low. At the same time, the moderately **reduced** levels of the PSD of β -rhythm in F7, P4, P3, T6 and T5 loci and Entropy in T5 locus as well as Shape Coefficient of GDI in Right projection (SC GDI R) are completely **normalized** (cluster B-/A0).

That is, there is a **normalizing** (ambivalence-equilibratory) effect as one of the attributes of adaptogens [1,11,18,25,33] according to the good old "law of initial level".

On the other hand, **normal** levels of cortisol and circulating catecholamines (1/Mo as HRV-marker), sympathetic tone (AMo as HRV-marker) as well as activity of ν -, μ - and β -rhythm generating neurons in 7 loci **also increase**, albeit slightly. This is accompanied by a rightward shift in the symmetry of δ -rhythm (cluster B0/A+).

The described changes in parameters of EEG, HRV, hormones and bioelectrophotonics are negatively/positively correlated with the changes in parameters of phagocytosis [5,22,36,52] (as well as of immunity [4,6,8,22,35,37,38,51]), so effects of the treatment are physiologically favorable and therefore adaptogenic.

The previously selected variables were further subjected to discriminant analysis with the aim not so much to discover which of them are formally characteristic, but to visualize the integral state of each volunteer. The forward stepwise program included only 14

Table 2

Clusters of adaptogenic effects as differences between levels ($Z \pm SE$) after and before treatment

Clusters and Variables	R	Before (30)	After (30)	Effect (30)
B+/A0		0,65±0,14	0,02±0,05	-0,63±0,11
Triiodothyronine	0,181	0,81±0,30	0,05±0,35	-0,77±0,28
T6-β PSD r	0,145	0,37±0,25	-0,03±0,16	-0,39±0,20
PSD LF band		1,27±0,69	0,19±0,44	-1,08±0,58
PSD HF band		0,51±0,44	-0,08±0,33	-0,59±0,30
Chakra 3 Asymmetry		0,41±0,28	-0,15±0,24	-0,56±0,33
Entropy GDI Left		0,53±0,21	0,15±0,20	-0,38±0,17
B0/A-		0,09±0,05	-0,42±0,03	-0,52±0,05
Testosterone	0,208	0,23±0,29	-0,50±0,21	-0,74±0,36
SDNN HRV	0,179	-0,13±0,17	-0,46±0,10	-0,33±0,17
RMSSD HRV		0,14±0,25	-0,33±0,19	-0,47±0,17
pNN ₅₀ HRV		0,26±0,38	-0,29±0,31	-0,56±0,22
PSD VLF band		0,03±0,28	-0,39±0,23	-0,42±0,27
Laterality-α		-0,07±0,17	-0,46±0,13	-0,39±0,20
Chakra 7 Asymmetry	0,204	0,17±0,22	-0,38±0,19	-0,54±0,23
AP MC(AVL) Laterality		0,11±0,21	-0,57±0,31	-0,68±0,36
B0/A+		0,04±0,05	0,56±0,07	+0,52±0,06
Cortisol	-0,182	0,05±0,27	0,64±0,23	+0,60±0,34
Asymmetry-δ	-0,162	-0,10±0,18	0,35±0,23	+0,46±0,25
T3-β PSD a	-0,166	0,30±0,23	1,20±0,55	+0,90±0,40
F3-β PSD a	-0,141	0,08±0,18	0,50±0,28	+0,43±0,24
T6-θ PSD a	-0,091	-0,04±0,19	0,87±0,57	+0,91±0,56
F8-β PSD a		-0,04±0,13	0,77±0,51	+0,81±0,46
P4-β PSD a		0,00±0,15	0,44±0,34	+0,44±0,23
C4-β PSD a		0,00±0,13	0,38±0,26	+0,38±0,20
C3-β PSD a		0,17±0,17	0,52±0,24	+0,35±0,19
C3-α PSD a		-0,16±0,15	0,19±0,27	+0,35±0,17
Amplitude of Mode HRV		0,26±0,21	0,70±0,23	+0,44±0,25
1/Mode HRV		0,10±0,26	0,58±0,25	+0,48±0,19
Microbial count for Staph. aur.		-0,16±0,11	0,14±0,14	+0,30±0,13
B-/A0		-0,82±0,18	-0,30±0,17	+0,52±0,13
Bactericidity vs E. coli	-0,349	-0,94±0,35	0,57±0,32	+1,50±0,35
Bactericidity vs Staph. aureus	-0,332	-1,64±0,28	-0,47±0,27	+1,16±0,38
Killing Index vs E. coli	-0,164	-2,05±0,15	-1,73±0,16	+0,33±0,15
Popovych's Adaptation Index-1		-1,91±0,32	-1,08±0,36	+0,83±0,43
T5-α PSD r	-0,097	-0,52±0,16	-0,32±0,15	+0,20±0,10
T6-α PSD a		-0,35±0,06	0,05±0,21	+0,39±0,17
T6-α PSD r		-0,55±0,12	-0,26±0,16	+0,30±0,16
P4-α PSD a		-0,24±0,12	-0,06±0,17	+0,18±0,08
P3-α PSD a		-0,19±0,15	0,00±0,22	+0,18±0,10
F7-α PSD r		-0,36±0,17	-0,04±0,17	+0,32±0,12
T5 PSD Entropy		-0,45±0,27	0,06±0,16	+0,51±0,26
Shape Coefficient Right (f)		-0,63±0,15	-0,36±0,16	+0,27±0,14

Fig. 6. Individual values of discriminant Root before (B) and after (A) course of intake of the Phytocomposition or the Naftussya water. A smaller column height reflects a decrease in variables positively correlated with the root, but an increase in variables inversely related to the root (please see Table 2)

Student's criterion (Tables 3-4), while other variables were outside the model, despite significant (*) changes (Tables 5-6). On the face of it, the Wilks' and Student's statistics do not match completely.

variables in the discriminant model, including those subject to non-significant ($t < 2,02$) effects according to the

On the basis of the raw coefficients and constant (Table 7), the individual values of the canonical discriminant roots were calculated with the following

Table 3

Discriminant Function Analysis Summary
 Step 14, N of vars in model: 14; Grouping: 2 grps;
 Wilks' Lambda: 0,4117; approx. $F_{(14)}=4,6$; $p<10^{-4}$

Variables currently in the model	State (n) and Mean±SE			Parameters of Wilks' Statistics					Refer Cv SD
	Before (30)	After (30)	Effect (30)	Wilks' Λ	Partial Λ	F-remove (1,45)	p-level	Tolerance	
T6- β PSD, %	35,9 4,1	29,4 2,7	-6,5 3,2*	0,439	0,939	2,94	0,093	0,582	29,8 0,554
T3- β PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	94 13	145 31	+50 23*	0,473	0,870	6,73	0,013	0,151	77 0,726
F3- β PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	83 10	106 15	+23 13	0,445	0,926	3,60	0,064	0,117	79 0,682
T5- α PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	25,7 2,9	29,2 2,7	+3,5 1,9	0,504	0,816	10,1	0,003	0,393	35,1 0,516
T6- θ PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	22 4	41 11	+18 11	0,428	0,962	1,77	0,190	0,732	23 0,869
Asymmetry- δ , %	39,3 4,3	50,3 5,5	+11,0 6,0	0,452	0,911	4,39	0,042	0,792	41,8 0,580
SDNN HRV, msec	52,0 5,1	42,2 3,2	-9,8 4,9*	0,414	0,995	0,21	0,651	0,453	55,9 0,531
Testosterone standardized, Z	+0,23 0,29	-0,50 0,21	-0,74 0,36*	0,466	0,883	5,96	0,019	0,726	0 0,500
Cortisol, nM/L	375 31	442 26	+67 38	0,436	0,945	2,63	0,112	0,641	370 0,303
Triiodothyronine, nM/L	2,61 0,15	2,22 0,18	-0,38 0,14*	0,431	0,955	2,12	0,152	0,756	2,20 0,227
Bactericidity vs E. coli, 10^9 B/L	89,5 3,5	104,4 3,1	+14,9 3,5*	0,421	0,979	0,98	0,329	0,351	99 0,100
Killing Index vs E. coli, %	42,2 1,5	45,3 1,5	+3,2 1,4*	0,446	0,923	3,78	0,058	0,293	62,0 0,156
Bactericidity vs St. aur., 10^9 B/L	88,4 2,9	100,7 2,8	+12,3 4,0*	0,431	0,956	2,07	0,157	0,491	106 0,100
Chakra 7 Asymmetry	0,08 0,05	-0,05 0,05	-0,13 0,05*	0,476	0,865	7,03	0,011	0,649	0,04 0,24

Notes. In each column, the first line is the average, the second – SE. In norm column - the average and Cv or SD. The "Effect" and "Norm" columns are not the result of discriminant analysis

Table 4

Summary of stepwise analysis of discriminant variables ranked by criterion Λ

Variables currently in the model	F to enter	p-level	Λ	F-value	p-value
Bactericidity vs E. coli, 10^9 B/L	10,1	0,002	0,852	10,1	0,002
SDNN HRV, msec	5,95	0,018	0,771	8,46	0,001
Chakra 7 Asymmetry	4,85	0,032	0,710	7,64	10^{-3}
Testosterone standardized, Z	5,62	0,021	0,644	7,60	10^{-4}
T6- β PSD, %	3,60	0,063	0,604	7,09	10^{-4}
Cortisol, nM/L	2,20	0,144	0,580	6,41	10^{-4}
T3- β PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	1,94	0,169	0,559	5,87	10^{-4}
Asymmetry- δ , %	1,95	0,168	0,538	5,47	10^{-4}
T5- α PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	3,04	0,087	0,507	5,40	10^{-4}
F3- β PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	3,11	0,084	0,477	5,37	10^{-4}
Killing Index vs E. coli, %	1,86	0,179	0,459	5,14	10^{-4}
Triiodothyronine, nM/L	1,59	0,213	0,444	4,90	10^{-4}
Bactericidity vs St. aur., 10^9 B/L	1,74	0,193	0,428	4,73	10^{-4}
T6- θ PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	1,77	0,190	0,412	4,59	10^{-4}

Fig. 7. Individual and average (M \pm SE) changes in discriminant Root at Female (F) and Male (M) caused by intake of the Balm (B) or the Naftussya water (N)

Fig. 8. Average (M \pm SE) values of discriminant Root before (B) and after (A) course of use of the Balm and the Naftussya water

visualization in Fig. 6.

As we can see, the reaction to both Phytocomposition and Naftussya water drinking takes place in almost all participants with some exception (Fig. 6), although the severity of the reaction has significant individual differences (Fig. 7), which is quite natural.

The accuracy of the retrospective classification of phytocomposition effects by calculating individual classification functions based on

Table 5

EEG variables currently not in the discriminant model

Variables currently not in the model	State (n) and Mean \pm SE			Parameters of Wilks' Statistics					Refer Cv SD
	Before (30)	After (30)	Effect (30)	Wilks' Λ	Partial Λ	F to enter	p-level	Tolerance	
Laterality- α , %	-3 6	-17 4	-13 7	0,408	0,990	0,45	0,504	0,639	-1 34
F7- α PSD, %	22,4 2,4	27,0 2,4	+4,6 1,7*	0,412	1,000	0,01	0,940	0,446	27,6 0,522
C3- α PSD, μ V ² /Hz	135 25	193 44	+58 29*	0,412	1,000	0,01	0,936	0,294	162 1,039
T6- α PSD, %	25,6 2,1	30,9 2,8	+5,3 2,8	0,411	0,999	0,03	0,873	0,256	35,5 0,502
T6- α PSD, μ V ² /Hz	63 9	121 32	+58 25*	0,412	1,000	10 ⁻⁴	0,994	0,506	114 1,302
P3- α PSD, μ V ² /Hz	216 55	286 84	+70 39	0,410	0,997	0,14	0,711	0,365	287 1,319
P4- α PSD, μ V ² /Hz	195 46	265 66	+70 29*	0,412	1,000	0,02	0,894	0,365	288 1,318
P4- β PSD, μ V ² /Hz	89 8	113 18	+24 13	0,412	1,000	0,01	0,918	0,291	89 0,611
P3- β PSD, μ V ² /Hz	104 10	120 16	+16 8*	0,411	0,999	0,05	0,827	0,276	93 0,665
C4- β PSD, μ V ² /Hz	96 8	121 17	+25 13	0,411	0,998	0,07	0,786	0,118	96 0,691
F8- β PSD, μ V ² /Hz	43 5	71 17	+28 16	0,409	0,993	0,30	0,583	0,446	44 0,771
C3- β PSD, μ V ² /Hz	96 8	121 17	+25 13	0,411	0,998	0,09	0,763	0,063	96 0,691
Entropy T5 PSD	0,767 0,035	0,833 0,021	+0,066 0,033*	0,411	0,999	0,05	0,832	0,652	0,825 0,156

Table 6

HRV, Immune and Biophysics variables currently not in the discriminant model

Variables currently not in the model	State (n) and Mean±SE			Parameters of Wilks' Statistics					
	Before (30)	After (30)	Effect (30)	Wilks' Λ	Partial Λ	F to enter	p-level	Tolerance	Refer Cv SD
Mode HRV, msec	864 26	822 26	-48 19*	0,412	1,000	10 ⁻⁵	0,999	0,627	874 0,115
Amplitude Mode HRV, %	43,6 2,9	48,4 2,9	4,8 2,8	0,407	0,989	0,48	0,490	0,796	39,2 0,329
RMSSD HRV, msec	30,9 3,8	24,0 2,9	-6,8 2,4*	0,410	0,996	0,17	0,683	0,221	29,4 0,482
pNN ₅₀ , %	11,6 3,0	6,7 2,3	-4,9 2,0*	0,412	1,000	0,01	0,910	0,284	9,0 0,846
PSD HF band, msec ²	545 153	360 110	-185 97	0,412	1,000	10 ⁻³	0,963	0,377	360 0,750
PSD LF band, msec ²	981 197	670 125	-310 153*	0,404	0,982	0,82	0,370	0,218	635 0,468
PSD VLF band, msec ²	1261 197	963 147	-298 185	0,408	0,991	0,39	0,535	0,750	1262 0,561
Microbial count for St. aur., B/Ph	60,0 1,1	63,0 1,3	+3,0 1,3*	0,411	0,999	0,03	0,866	0,445	61,6 0,160
Popovych's Adaptation Index-1	1,24 0,08	1,44 0,09	+0,20 0,10*	0,410	0,996	0,18	0,968	0,725	1,71 0,245
AP MC(AVL) Laterality, %	+0,2 0,4	-1,1 0,6	-1,3 0,7	0,412	1,000	0,01	0,904	0,730	0 1,9
Shape Coefficient GDI Right (f), un	13,28 0,25	13,71 0,25	+0,43 0,23	0,411	0,999	0,05	0,832	0,726	14,30 0,114
Entropy GDI Left	3,83 0,03	3,77 0,03	-0,05 0,02*	0,412	1,000	10 ⁻³	0,968	0,725	3,75 0,038
Chakra 3 Asymmetry	0,15 0,06	0,02 0,06	-0,13 0,07	0,410	0,996	0,18	0,670	0,717	0,06 0,23

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Table 7

Standardized and raw coefficients and constant for discriminant variables

Variables	Coefficients	
	Standardized	Raw
Bactericidity vs E. coli, 10 ⁹ B/L	-0,321	-0,018
SDNN HRV, msec	0,131	0,006
Chakra 7 Asymmetry	0,595	2,180
Testosterone standardized, Z	0,523	0,513
T6- β PSD, %	0,423	0,022
Cortisol, nM/L	-0,382	-0,002
T3- β PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	-1,210	-0,009
Asymmetry- δ , %	-0,437	-0,015
T5- α PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	-0,891	-0,057
F3- β PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	1,037	0,015
Killing Index vs E. coli, %	-0,670	-0,082
Triiodothyronine, nM/L	0,318	0,354
Bactericidity vs St. aur., 10 ⁹ B/L	-0,390	-0,025
T6- θ PSD, $\mu V^2/Hz$	-0,296	-0,281
	Constant	8,671
	Eigenvalue	1,429
Squared Mahalanobis Distance=5,52; F ₍₁₄₎ =4,5; p<10 ⁻⁴		
Canonical R=0,767; Wilks' Λ =0,4117; $\chi^2_{(14)}$ =45; p<10 ⁻⁴		

its coefficients and constants (Table 8) is 90% (Table 9).

The adrenomimetic effect of both "Balm Kryms'kyi" and ginseng tincture on the isolated heart of a frog [1], due to

inhibition of catechol-o-methyltransferase activity [39], is associated with polyphenols.

However, we are inclined to the neurogenic mechanism of the adreno-

Table 8

Coefficients and constants of classification functions

Variables	Clusters	Before 0,500	After 0,500
Bactericidity vs <i>E. coli</i> , 10 ⁹ B/L		-0,408	-0,366
SDNN HRV, msec		0,391	0,378
Chakra 7 Asymmetry		-8,295	-13,42
Testosterone standardized, Z		-2,603	-3,808
T6-β PSD, %		0,074	0,022
Cortisol, nM/L		0,057	0,063
T3-β PSD, μV ² /Hz		0,031	0,053
Asymmetry-δ, %		0,177	0,214
T5-α PSD, μV ² /Hz		0,604	0,739
F3-β PSD, μV ² /Hz		-0,011	-0,046
Killing Index vs <i>E. coli</i> , %		1,608	1,800
Triiodothyronine, nM/L		-1,373	-2,204
Bactericidity vs <i>St. aur.</i> , 10 ⁹ B/L		0,893	0,951
T6-θ PSD, μV ² /Hz		2,081	2,741
	Constants	-87,54	-107,9

sympathomimetic effect of the phytochemicals revealed in this study. This is consistent with literature data on the direct neurotropic effect of phytoadaptogens in vitro and in vivo [2,43-45], as well as our data on changes in EEG parameters.

The figures presented by Winkelmann T et al [60] give us reason to assume that the loci C3/C4 projected precentral gyrus, T3/T4 – inferior temporal gyrus, F3/F4 - caudal anterior cingulate cortex or rostral middle frontal gyrus, P3/P4 – supramarginal gyrus, T5/T6 – transverse temporal cortex. The **thickness** of these cortical structures is positively correlated with the HF HRV as marker of vagal tone. However, according to our data, an increase in **electrical activity**, or more precisely PSD, of neurons that project to the listed loci is

accompanied by a moderate, within the normal range, decrease in vagal tone, as well as plasma levels of testosterone and triiodothyronine in combination with a moderate increase in the levels of cortisol and circulating catecholamines. This is consistent with the concept that adaptogens are **eustress** inducers that prevent the development of **distress** under the influence of pathogenic factors [19,20,33,34,46].

In previous studies of our laboratory, in line with the concept of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex [49], relationships between EEG and HRV [50,53], EEG&HRV and adaptogene hormones [31,48], EEG&HRV and immunity [22,35-38,48,51,52] parameters were tracked in detail.

With regard to the mechanism of the neurotropic action of phytochemicals, in particular polyphenols, we suggest the mediating role of aryl hydrocarbon receptors of neurons [29,30,41]. The possibility of irritation by phytochemicals of the chemoreceptor terminals of the afferent vagal fibers in the intestine with subsequent influence on the activity of CNS neurons should not be rejected [14].

In conclusion, we will discuss the place and role of biophotonics and

Table 9

Classification Matrix

Group	Rows: Observed classifications Columns: Predicted classifications		
	Percent Correct	B p=,50000	A p=,50000
Before	90,0	27	3
After	90,0	3	27
Total	90,0	30	30

acupuncture parameters in the adaptogenic effects of the phytocomposition. Previously, it was shown in our laboratory that GDV parameters significantly correlate with parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex [3-6,8,9] and acupuncture points [7] and respond to the influence of another adaptogen - Naftussya bioactive water [23]. Unidirectional changes in the symmetry of the third and seventh Chakras, electrical conductivity of acupuncture points MC(AVL) (represent the immune system) and EEG alpha-rhythm as well as opposite changes in the delta-rhythm were found in this study. According to Ayurveda **third Chakra** associated with **celiac plexus ganglion** and **spleen** as well as [endocrine] pancreas, liver, gall bladder, stomach, duodenum, pancreas; **seventh Chakra** - with **right** (paired EEG loci) and upper brain as well as pineal gland [13]. Therefore, these parameters of biophotonics and acupuncture logically fit into the structure of the anti-inflammatory cholinergic reflex [14].

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Accordance To Ethics Standards

Tests in patients are carried out in accordance with positions of Helsinki Declaration 1975, revised and complemented in 2002, and directive of National Committee on ethics of scientific researches. During realization of tests from all participants the informed consent is got and used all measures for providing of anonymity of participants.

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